

A CNDO Theoretical Study of $(\text{H}_3\text{B}-\text{NO})^+$

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A CNDO level theoretical study of the formation, stability and charge transfer of the addition compound between BH_3 and $(\text{NO})^+$ shows a net electron transfer from BH_3 to $(\text{NO})^+$. The donation stems from $(\text{NO})^+$ 3σ into BH_3 $2a_1^*$, while the back-donation stems from the formally occupied s -orbitals of BH_3 into the formally unoccupied π^* orbitals of $(\text{NO})^+$ and over-compensates the donation.

BORANE (BH_3) and its various derivatives are known to form stable addition compounds with suitable donors^{1,2}. The nitric oxide, NO , is known to form coordination complexes in three different states of oxidation: NO , $(\text{NO})^-$ and $(\text{NO})^+$, of which $(\text{NO})^+$, the nitrosonium cation, is the most effective ligand³. We have recently performed a theoretical study of the compound of $(\text{NO})^-$ with BH_3 ^{4,5}. The present paper describes a theoretical study of the formation and stability of the addition compound of BH_3 with $(\text{NO})^+$. The origin of charge transfer and bond formation are also investigated.

Experimental

Method of computation: The compound formation is allowed by approaching the B-end of BH_3 towards the N-end of $(\text{NO})^+$ along the C_2 -axis so that the B-N bond is coincident with the C_2 -axis. The geometric parameters of the complex $(\text{H}_3\text{B}-\text{NO})^+$ are optimised by the CNDO/2 method with standard parameters⁶ to obtain the equilibrium geometry. The gross orbital and overlap populations of $(\text{H}_3\text{B}-\text{NO})^+$ at the CNDO/2 equilibrium geometry and of BH_3 and $(\text{NO})^+$ at the same nuclear configuration as in the adduct, are computed through CNDO/2D method⁷. The occupation numbers of the MO's of the donor and the acceptor species in interaction are computed, after the chemical interaction leading to the adduct formation, following the CNDO/2D adapted method of Fukui^{8,9}.

The computed CNDO/2D gross orbital populations are listed in Table 1. The computed occupation numbers of the MO's of the donor and the MO's of the acceptor species are listed in Table 2. The orbital pairwise breakdowns of the overlap populations of the newly formed B-N bond and the contributions of the orbital interactions of the MO's of BH_3 and $(\text{NO})^+$ towards the formation of the new bond are shown in Table 3.

The optimised equilibrium geometric parameters of the nitrosyl borane, $(\text{H}_3\text{B}-\text{NO})^+$, are shown in

TABLE 1—THE GROSS ORBITAL POPULATIONS

AO	Donor-acceptor	Adduct
	$\text{BH}_3 (C_{2v})$	$(\text{H}_3\text{B}-\text{NO})^+$
B_{2s}	1.068 2	1.016 7
$\pi (B_{2p})$	0.823 4	0.860 9
B_{2p_z}	0.041 5	0.335 1
H_{1s}	1.081 2	0.845 9
	$(\text{NO})^+$	
N_{2s}	1.791 8	1.654 9
$\pi (N_{2p})$	0.737 6	0.877 5
N_{2p_z}	1.067 6	1.189 6
O_{2s}	1.852 1	1.849 3
$\pi (O_{2p})$	1.262 4	1.403 7
O_{2p_z}	1.288 5	1.154 5

TABLE 2—OCCUPATION NUMBERS OF THE MO'S OF THE BH_3 AND $(\text{NO})^+$ FRAGMENTS OF $(\text{H}_3\text{B}-\text{NO})^+$ AFTER CHEMICAL INTERACTION

$\text{BH}_3 (C_{2v})$		$(\text{NO})^+$	
MO	ν_i	MO	ν_i
$1a_1$	1.951 8	1σ	2.009 2
$1e$	1.703 3	2σ	1.943 5
$2e$	1.703 3	1π	1.994 0
$2a_1^*$	0.211 0	2π	1.994 0
$3a_1^*$	0.001 0	3σ	1.867 0
$3e^*$	0.015 5	$3\pi^*$	0.287 2
$4e^*$	0.015 5	$4\pi^*$	0.287 2
		$4\sigma^*$	0.016 5
	= 5.601 4		= 10.398 6
	(- 0.398 6)		(+ 0.398 6)

TABLE 3—BREAKDOWNS OF THE B-N BOND POPULATION AND CONTRIBUTION OF ORBITAL ACCORDING TO THE INTERACTION* BETWEEN MO'S OF BH_3 AND MO'S OF $(\text{NO})^+$

Orbital pairs	Populations	I	II	III	IV
B_{2s}/N_{2s}	-0.151 4	-0.170 6	0.029 6	-0.005 8	-0.004 6
B_{2s}/N_{2p}	-0.021 9	-0.063 2	0.030 5	0.006 0	0.004 7
B_{2p}/N_{2s}	0.213 7	0.037 4	0.187 7	0.001 3	-0.012 5
B_{2p}/N_{2p}	0.109 4	0.011 1	0.088 7	-0.001 1	0.010 5
$\pi(2p_x/2p_x)$	0.116 1	-0.016 5	0.009 8	0.106 3	0.016 5
$\pi(2p_y/2p_y)$	0.116 1	-0.016 5	0.009 8	0.106 3	0.016 5

*Interaction between: (I)=occupied MO's of BH_3 and occupied MO's of $(\text{NO})^+$, (II)=unoccupied MO's of BH_3 and occupied MO's of $(\text{NO})^+$, (III)=occupied MO's of BH_3 and unoccupied MO's of $(\text{NO})^+$ and (IV)=unoccupied MO's of BH_3 and unoccupied MO's of $(\text{NO})^+$.

Fig. 1. The gas phase heat of formation is -183.7 kcal mol $^{-1}$. The charge distribution in the donor, the acceptor and the adduct is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. Geometric parameters of $(H_3B-NO)^+$.

Fig. 2. Charge distribution in the donor, acceptor and adduct.

Results and Discussions

Electric structure and Mulliken population analysis: The molecule $(BH_3-NO)^+$ belongs to C_{3v} point group and the ground state electronic configuration is $1a_1^2 2a_1^2 3a_1^2 1e^2 2e^2 4a_1^2 3e^2 4e^2$. Since $(NO)^+$ is iso-electronic with CO, one can expect that the pattern of chemical binding and the charge transfer action in nitrosyl borane will mimic those of carbonyl borane. The formal charges on B of BH_3 and on N of $(NO)^+$ are positive (Fig. 2). Thus the formation of $(H_3B-NO)^+$, similar to the formation of (H_3B-CO) , the carbonyl borane 7 , involves the joining of two fragments through their positively charged ends. The charge density distribution in the donor and the acceptor undergoes a thorough change during chemical interaction, viz. the formal charge on B changes from positive to negative, that on H-atoms is depleted considerably, the positive charges on N and O are reduced considerably. This suggests a strong electron density transfer from the H atoms of BH_3 to the other part of the molecule during the reorganisation of the overall pattern of charge density. The populations of B_{2s} and N_{2s} , O_{2s} , O_{2p_z} , H_{1s} orbitals decrease but those of B_{2p_z} , N_{2p_z} and $\pi(B_{2p})$, $\pi(N_{2p})$, $\pi(O_{2p})$ orbitals increase (Table 1). The change in the population of H_{1s} and B_{2p_z} orbitals are very sharp. The N_{2s} and N_{2p_z} orbitals donate charge to the B_{2s}

and B_{2p_z} orbitals which pass charge on to the other part of the acceptor unit in the 'spill-over effect'. In this 'spill-over process' 9 the B_{2s} orbital has lost all charge received by it including a part originally residing on it. In the 'pile up effect' 9 the O_{2s} and O_{2p_z} orbitals transfer charge to N_{2s} and N_{2p_z} orbitals whereby the initial loss in N_{2p_z} is over-compensated. Significant increase in the π -populations of all the AO's and large depletion of charge density around H-atoms due to complex formation suggest a hyperconjugative mechanism of back-donation like that in carbonyl borane 1,7,10 is also operative in nitrosyl borane as is evident from the examination of occupation numbers of the MO's.

Charge transfer and bond formation: Table 2 demonstrates that in the donation step charge is removed from 3σ , the HOMO, of $(NO)^+$, the formal donor and is placed into $2a_1^*$, the LUMO, of BH_3 , the formal acceptor, while in the back-donation step charge is transferred from the formally occupied e -orbitals of BH_3 into the formally unoccupied π^* (orbitals empty before the interaction are starred) orbitals of $(NO)^+$. The intramolecular charge rearrangement is insignificant and the amount of net charge transfer is 0.3986 a.u. from BH_3 to $(NO)^+$.

The orbital overlap interactions-I and -IV (Table 3) between the occupied MO's of BH_3 and the occupied MO's of $(NO)^+$ as well as that between the unoccupied MO's of BH_3 and the unoccupied MO's of $(NO)^+$ make either antibonding or very little contribution to the formation of the new bond and as such the interactions between these orbitals are insignificant in the process of charge transfer. On the other hand, the donation interaction-II between the occupied MO's of $(NO)^+$ with the unoccupied MO's of BH_3 is predominantly σ -type and while the back-donation interaction-III between the occupied MO's of BH_3 and the unoccupied MO's of $(NO)^+$ is predominantly π -type, and these two interactions are the most dominating charge-transfer interaction in the formation of $(H_3B-NO)^+$ complex. The changes in the occupation numbers of the orbitals involved in the donation (3σ and $2a_1^*$) and the back-donation (e and π^*) reveal that the amount of the charge transferred in the back-donation process is nearly treble the amount of charge transferred in the donation process. Because of this trend in the dominating charge transfer effects, the net balance sheet of charge transfer shows that a considerable amount of charge is transferred from the formal acceptor to the formal donor.

The new B-N bond is of pivotal importance in the formation of the compound. Table 3 shows that the populations of B_{2s}/N_{2s} and B_{2s}/N_{2p_z} orbital pairs are negative (antibonding) and the newly formed σ -bond principally arises from the combination of B_{2p_z} and N_{2s} and $2p_z$ atomic orbitals. The sum of the two π -populations is greater than

Fig. 3. Donation and back-donation of the charge transfer process.

the σ -population and hence the hyperconjugation (Fig. 3) plays the major part in charge transfer as well as in the formation of B-N bond in $(H_3B-NO)^+$.

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